

Landen, *Konijnenberg* (Belgium): a Final Middle Paleolithic site

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ABSTRACT

The open-air site of *Landen-Konijnenberg* in Central Belgium was discovered in the 1980s during a fieldwalking survey. Based on a limited amount of lithics originating from the ploughsoil, the site could only be broadly dated to the Middle Paleolithic. In recent years, the location has been intensively surveyed again. This yielded some diagnostic material, allowing the site to be dated more precisely to the final phase of the Middle Paleolithic. This preliminary paper provides a description of some diagnostic finds belonging to this Landen assemblage. Some artefacts suggest a clear relationship with the technocomplex/transitional industry of the *Lincombian-Ranisian-Jerzmanowician* (LRJ) and quite possibly even the Aurignacian, dating to the beginning of the Upper Paleolithic.

KEYWORDS

Fieldwalking survey
Belgian Loess Belt
Wommersom quartzite (WSQ)
Discoïd-Denticulate Mousterian
Fäustel
Jerzmanowice point
Lincombian-Ranisian-Jerzmanowician (LRJ)
Aurignacian
Landen assemblage

1. Introduction

In the context of preparing a PhD¹, Prof. Marc Lodewijckx (emeritus at the Catholic University of Leuven) once surveyed a large area of arable land in Landen, a municipality located in the loess region of central Belgium. At the location named *Konijnenberg*, he encountered a concentration of heavily patinated flint artefacts. Due to the limited number of lithics, it was only possible to propose a general dating of the assemblage to the Middle Paleolithic period. The findspot was entered into the database of the Central Archaeological Inventory (managed by the Flemish government agency *Onroerend Erfgoed*) as CAI-location 336. However, the finds were never since been studied in detail or published. From 2012 onwards, I have surveyed the location on numerous occasions, during which several diagnostic finds were collected. Based on this material, a more precise dating for the site could be provided, specifically the final phase of the Middle Paleolithic.

2. Geographical setting

The site is located along the northern margin of the central Belgian loess belt which extends across parts of northern and central Europe. The local topography is shaped by the course of the Kleine Gete River, part of the Scheldt river basin. Prehistoric humans chose an elevated location near the head of a spring valley subsequently infilled with colluvium. This former spring valley connected to the valley of the Kleine Gete, which currently flows about 550 meters southeast of the site. At the findspot, the Quaternary cover is relatively thin, with Cenozoic sediments locally exposed at the surface. Remains of a Roman villa (1st to 3rd century AD) - located just south of the find concentration - may have caused some disturbance to the subsoil.

Fig. 1: Site location and the current topo-/hydrographical conditions.

¹ LODEWIJCKX 1988.

3. The lithic assemblage

3.1 Raw materials

All artifacts were made from regionally available raw materials, namely flint and quartzite. Deposits with high-quality flint are exposed along the upper course of the Kleine Gete, where numerous Paleolithic open-air (workshop) sites have been found.² Characteristic flint nodules from this region were transported further downstream by hunter-gatherers towards the site in Landen. However, most artifacts were made from (eluvial) fine-grained Hesbaye flint with a mottled grey color. Among the other raw materials used was Wommersom quartzite (WSQ). This stone outcrops at one specific location nearby the village of Wommersom, approximately 2.5 km north of the site. To date, only isolated Middle Paleolithic WSQ artifacts have been found in this region, including a handaxe (CAI-location 1629).³

Unfortunately, the Landen assemblage has been heavily affected by glacial conditions after the occupation phase. Hereafter, only the most diagnostic artifacts - which possess an adequate number of relevant attributes - will be described and illustrated.

3.2 Diagnostic artifacts of a Discoid-Denticulate Mousterian⁴

A very characteristic aspect of the Landen assemblage is the frequent occurrence of rather small-sized denticulated and notched tools (fig. 2). Notches were often applied in a specific way, resulting in "nosed" pieces. Also noteworthy is the shaping of some tools by a ventral retouch, including a *racloir sur talon* (fig. 3). A lot of unmodified flint and WSQ flakes and blades exhibit dihedral and complex (faceted) striking platforms (fig. 4), which serves as an indicator of the prepared core technique. The (prepared) cores are rather small (exhausted) and usually discoid-shaped (fig. 5).

3.3 Small handaxe (*Faüstel*)

So far, the Landen assemblage includes one fragment of a flint handaxe (fig. 6). It is a small and relatively thin specimen with a rather flat side and a more convex side, respectively covered with a homogeneous white patina and a spotted/*vermiculé*-patina.⁵ Due to its thickness, the artifact has been identified as a *Fäustel* rather than a bifacially shaped leafpoint (of the *Mauern* type).

3.4 Jerzmanowice point (fragment)

A single fragment of a flint Jerzmanowice point (fig. 7) was found in 2018. The J-point is broken and burinated, which can be interpreted as traces from impact.⁶ Another possibility is that it concerns a recycled, broken point to produce a new tool (*in casu* a burin).⁷ In this specific case, preference is given to an impact-related damage, considering the rather irregular fracture patterns. Especially the Beedings assemblage (open-air site in West Sussex, Great-Britain) contains similar examples of impact-damaged or recycled blade points.⁸ It should be noted that this artefact is made from a fine-grained flint with a homogeneous to finely laminated texture and a rather dark grey color. At first glance, these features do not correspond within the spectrum of the regionally occurring flint variants, so it could therefore be an imported flint type from an extra-regional origin.

² VAN DIJCK & OTTE 2019.

³ VAN PEER 1981.

⁴ See JAUBERT *ET AL.* 2012.

⁵ A less intense patina on a specific side of an artefact could be the result of *capping*.

⁶ See FLAS 2011; DEMIDENKO & ŠKRDLA 2023.

⁷ See POPE *ET AL.* 2013.

⁸ JACOBI 2007.

Fig. 2: Selection of denticulated and notched tools.

Fig. 3: Racloir sur talon.

Fig. 4: Selection of unmodified flakes and blades.

Fig. 5: Selection of (prepared) cores.

Fig. 6: *Fäustel*.

Fig. 7: Broken and burinated Jerzmanowice point.

3.5 Endscraper

An endscraper, made from Hesbaye flint (bearing a heavily patinated ventral surface), is fashioned on a robust, broken (retouched) blade (fig. 8). Morphologically, this artifact would fit well within an early Upper Paleolithic (Aurignacian) industry.

Fig. 8: Endscraper.

4. Conclusion

Based on the characteristics of the entire collection, we can assume that the location was visited by hunter-gatherers during the period between 45,000 and 38,000 BP. What makes the Landen assemblage specifically interesting is the co-occurrence of a Discoid-Denticulate Mousterian and the transitional industry of the *Lincombian-Ranisian-Jerzmanowician* (LRJ). The question remains as to whether the endscraper indicates an early Upper Paleolithic influence... or that it belongs to the transitional industry.

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